
sampleworks Design Document

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1 Motivation

Protein/biomolecular structure prediction models are trained on single state structures and fail to accurately predict the ensemble of conformations each protein/macromolecule occupies. However, these models show signs of capturing aspects of the underlying distribution of realistic macromolecular structures. We want to utilize the prior represented by structure prediction models and additional experimental observations to improve the sampling of the underlying ensemble present in the experiment and use this information to understand biomolecular function and improve ensemble prediction.

Currently, each structure prediction model has a different implementation, requiring bespoke boilerplate code to plug each model into experimental guidance. Our goal is to resolve this and expand the experimental methods we can provide guidance with. This will open new opportunities for model evaluation directly against experimental data, and help unlock new sources of data for training the next generation of biomolecular structure predictors.

2 Goals and Non-Goals

2.1 Goals:

- Implement model-agnostic biomolecular ensemble guidance with experimental data
 - Minimize boilerplate
 - Maintain minimal computational overhead compared to unguided sampling
- Maximize compatibility with existing experimental data formats and ML frameworks
- Expose evaluation methodology for systematic comparisons of different types of guidance and different generative models on experimental data
- Develop metrics and datasets as a testbed for generating hypotheses about future directions in model development and guidance method development
- Support comparison against multiple relevant types of experimental data, starting with real-space density maps

2.2 Non-Goals:

- Implement a new dependency that will bog down model development
- Require developers to acquire detailed knowledge of the framework to plug-and-play with new models

2.3 Long-Term Goals:

- Refine and improve abstractions so that us and other developers or agents can implement new modules to test new methods for guidance

- Support all relevant experimental techniques
- Make *sampleworks* the best platform for testing ensemble prediction
- Make *sampleworks* the most usable and capable platform for generating ensembles in real structural workflows
 - Support the cycle of iterative generation, refinement, and model training for improving the atomic models we use to understand biological function
- Develop relevant metrics for judging the reasonableness of ensemble models
 - Considering aspects like the data/parameter ratio and cross-validation metrics
- Improvement of solvent (bulk and explicit) modeling to enable improved fitting of structure factors & intensities

3 Key Design Decisions

4 *sampleworks* technical architecture

sampleworks consists of four primary interfaces that enable methods that produce arbitrary coordinates (generally we assume these are structure prediction models) to interact compositably with methods for inference time steering or guidance. These four interfaces are called **ModelWrappers** (of which there are 3 types), **Samplers**, **StepScalers**, and **TrajectoryScalers**.

Figure 1: *sampleworks* data flow diagram

4.1 ModelWrappers

The first core abstraction in *sampleworks* is the **ModelWrapper** protocol. There are three **ModelWrapper** protocol types, each of which define a minimal interface that generative model developers must implement to be usable with the rest of *sampleworks*. The primary goal is integration of models we don't control without requiring modifications to their source code or excessive boilerplate.

4.1.1 ModelWrapper variants

The three main `ModelWrapper` types are the `StructureModelWrapper`, `FlowModelWrapper`, and `EnergyBasedModelWrapper`. The `FlowModelWrapper` is the only `ModelWrapper` that has existing implementations following the protocol, though we aim to update this soon with the addition of latent-space guidance methods. An annotated `FlowModelWrapper` implementation is walked through in [the Boltz-2 appendix](#).

Each `ModelWrapper` protocol requires these two methods:

```
1 def featurize(self, structure: dict) -> GenerativeModelInput
```

python

```
1 def step(self, *, features: GenerativeModelInput) ->
  GenerativeModelOutputT
```

python

For the `StructureModelWrapper`, that is all that is required. The `StructureModelWrapper` is the most abstract, and enables any arbitrary input features to be generated from `featurize` and structures to be generated from `step` for usage in the iterative optimization in the guidance loop.

The `featurize` method converts an [Atomworks](#) structure dictionary (containing atomic coordinates, elements, B-factors, sequences, experimental metadata, and arbitrary atom annotations) into the features that the underlying model expects. In models that use Atomworks, this should be a wrapper around some sort of transform pipeline. `featurize` returns a `GenerativeModelInput`, a small container bundling `x_init` (the initial inputs with shape `(*batch, atoms, 3)`, either a reference structure (e.g. for alignment during sampling) or a noisy sample drawn from the prior in a diffusion or flow model) with a model-specific `conditioning`. The `conditioning` can be an arbitrary object, but we have found it useful to define a dataclass holding all the relevant cached attributes for reuse across steps. This `GenerativeModelInput` must be consumable by `step`.

The `step` method performs a single forward pass through the model and returns outputs consumable by the guidance loop, generally coordinates. The guidance loop is implemented by a [TrajectoryScaler](#). For general guidance methods, **this imposes a differentiability requirement**.

For diffusion and flow models specifically, the `FlowModelWrapper` protocol requires the current state `x_t` and timestep parameter `t` to `step`. The value returned by `step` for a `FlowModelWrapper` is a PyTorch Tensor or JAX Array of the predicted clean sample. Models parametrized in ways other than denoised prediction (ϵ -prediction, v -parametrization) will still need to return the predicted clean sample in `step`, which is a simple transformation. The `FlowModelWrapper` must also implement `initialize_from_prior`, which draws an initial state from the model's prior (Gaussian noise for diffusion/flow models), sized by the requested `batch_size` and the atom count carried by the features (or an explicit shape).

```
1 def step(
2     self,
3     x_t: Float[Array, "*batch atoms 3"],
4     t: Float[Array, "*batch"],
5     *,
6     features: GenerativeModelInput | None = None,
7 ) -> GenerativeModelOutputT
```

python

```

1 def initialize_from_prior( python
2     self,
3     batch_size: int,
4     features: GenerativeModelInput | None = None,
5     *,
6     shape: tuple[int, ...] | None = None,
7 ) -> GenerativeModelOutputT

```

Lastly, we support the energy-based regime of models and newer methods like Equilibrium Matching [1] and Energy Matching [2] with the `EnergyBasedModelWrapper`, whose step should return a PyTorch Tensor or JAX Array representing the vector field corresponding to the gradient of the model's energy function. The step method requires a parameter `x` corresponding to the state along with the optional conditioning features.

```

1 def step( python
2     self,
3     x: Float[Array, "*batch atoms 3"],
4     *,
5     features: GenerativeModelInput | None = None,
6 ) -> GenerativeModelOutputT

```

All these step methods return `GenerativeModelOutput`, which for current models is the coordinates: `Float[Array, "batch atoms 3"]`. This is subject to change depending on the exact model type, and the `ModelWrapper` Protocols are parametrized for this as class `ModelWrapper(Protocol[GenerativeModelOutputT])`, where `GenerativeModelOutputT` is the domain of the generative model.

4.2 Samplers

We also define various methods of sampling from `ModelWrappers` with `Samplers`. `Samplers` implement procedures for generating samples from the model, for example the `AF3EDMSampler` implements the Euler's method variant based on EDM [3] that AlphaFold 3 [4] and related methods use, while a (yet-to-be-implemented) `AnnealedLangevinSampler` would implement the Annealed Langevin SDE from Chroma [5].

Both `FlowModelWrapper` and `EnergyBasedModelWrapper` implementations require some sort of numerical solver to sample structures from. We implement these in the form of a new protocol, `Sampler`, which defines specific solvers to use for sampling from the SDE/ODE the `ModelWrapper` is parametrized for.

The `Sampler` protocol is deliberately *stateless*: it receives everything it needs through its arguments and returns updated state, so the same solver can drive a lone optimization or be embedded inside a population-level method without carrying hidden state between calls. Beyond a `check_context` validator that confirms the per-step parameters are compatible with the solver, its workhorse is `step` (not to be confused with the `ModelWrapper` `step` - perhaps a sign for renaming!):

```

1 def step( python
2     self,

```

```

3     state: StateT,
4     model_wrapper: ModelWrapperT,
5     context: StepParams,
6     *,
7     scaler: StepScalerProtocol | None = None,
8     features: GenerativeModelInput | None = None,
9 ) -> SamplerStepOutput[StateT]

```

This single interface spans two distinct modes of operation. Trajectory-based solvers (diffusion, flow-matching) integrate along a time/noise schedule and read `t`, `dt`, and `noise_scale` from the step context, while optimization-based solvers (gradient descent toward a reward, or equilibrium sampling for an `EnergyBasedModelWrapper`) instead read a `learning_rate`. The same `step` serves both, and metadata from `StepParams` reports what information is present.

`TrajectorySampler` is the trajectory specialization of `Sampler`, bound to `FlowModelWrappers`. It adds schedule management: `compute_schedule(num_steps)` builds a `SamplerSchedule` once, `check_schedule` validates it, and `get_context_for_step(step_index, schedule)` reads from it to construct the `StepParams` for each step. `AF3EDMSampler` is the concrete `TrajectorySampler` currently implemented.

Every step is driven by a single `StepParams`, the universal per-step context shared across samplers and scalers; different sampler types populate different fields:

```

1  class StepParams: python
2      step_index: int
3      total_steps: int | None = None
4
5      # Trajectory parameters (diffusion / flow-matching)
6      t: Float[Array, "batch"] | None = None # current time / noise
        level
7      dt: Float[Array, "batch"] | None = None # step size in time
8      noise_scale: Float[Array, "batch"] | None = None # std. dev. of noise at
        this t
9
10     # Optimization parameters
11     learning_rate: Float[Array, "batch"] | None = None
12
13     # Guidance parameters (optional, for guided sampling)
14     reward: RewardFunctionProtocol | None = None
15     reward_inputs: RewardInputs | None = None
16
17     # Optional atom reconciliation between structures and alignment reference
18     reconciler: AtomReconciler | None = None
19     alignment_reference: Float[Array, "*batch atoms 3"] | None = None
20
21     # Optional extra metadata (e.g. momentum velocity, cached noisy state)
22     metadata: dict[str, Any] | None = None

```

Here `reward` and `reward_inputs` carry the guidance target and its pre-extracted inputs (see [Loss Functions](#)), while `reconciler` and `alignment_reference` together let the sampler align model coordinates into the experimental reference frame before a reward is evaluated. Functional updaters (`with_reward`, `with_reconciler`, `with_metadata`) return modified copies.

A step returns a `SamplerStepOutput`, which bundles the updated `state` with optional additional attributes useful for trajectory tracking, such as the denoised prediction \hat{x}_θ , the scalar `loss` when guidance was applied, and a `log_proposal_correction` term consumed by trajectory-level resampling. The `SamplerSchedule` returned by `compute_schedule` is itself an immutable, sampler-specific container of the per-step arrays (e.g. the noise schedule) that `get_context_for_step` reads.

4.3 Scalers

When we talk about “scalers” and “scaling”, we are referring to ways of applying the model to a task it wasn’t directly trained on. Guidance is a subset of scaling, where we are aiming to sample from some posterior distribution $p(x|y)$ where the model is trained to sample from $p(x)$ and y is an experimental observation.

Each guidance type should take a specified `ModelWrapper` type as one of its initialization parameters, one or multiple experimental `LossFunctions` as another parameter, a sampling procedure, and a set of guidance parameters/hyperparameters. The guidance protocol should consume the outputs from the model step and experimental `Loss(s)` to do guidance with the model.

We implement guidance by observing that there are two broad types: the first involves modifying the score function in the `Sampler` to incorporate some `LossFunction`. This is what methods like Diffusion Posterior Sampling (DPS) [6] and the more recent versions building on it do. Concretely, this involves applying some algorithm before taking the next integration step in the numerical solver of the SDE/ODE. The second involves evolving many particles and reweighting/resampling to sample from a distribution tilted by a reward function (e.g. Feynman-Kač steering [7], DriftLite [8]). These types of guidance can be composable, as Boltz-1/2x do with Feynman-Kač steering and DPS [9]. To accomplish this, we define two main `Scaler` protocols, `StepScalerProtocol` and `TrajectoryScalerProtocol`.

4.3.1 StepScaler

The `StepScalerProtocol` is a standalone protocol that a `Sampler` consumes through the optional `scaler` argument of `Sampler.step`. It exposes two methods:

```

1 def scale(
2     self,
3     state: ModelOutputT,
4     context: StepParams,
5     *,
6     model: ModelWrapperT | None = None,
7 ) -> tuple[ModelOutputT, Float[Array, "batch"]]
8
9 def guidance_strength(self, context: StepParams) -> Float[Array, "batch"]

```

`scale` reads the `reward` and `reward_inputs` from the `StepParams`, computes the gradient of the `LossFunction` with respect to the coordinates, and returns a guidance direction together with the scalar loss value; `guidance_strength` supplies the timestep dependent weight applied to that direction. The sampler combines the two when forming the next state.

Diffusion Posterior Sampling-type methods come in two flavors that differ in where the gradient is taken [6]. Our implementations are as follows: `DataSpaceDPSScaler` backpropagates only through the denoised prediction \hat{x}_θ (cheap, since it avoids backpropagating through the network), while `NoiseSpaceDPSScaler` backpropagates through the full model to the noisy input `x_t`, which has been more accurate in our hands but requires the sampler to retain `x_t` with gradients enabled.

4.3.2 TrajectoryScaler

The `TrajectoryScalerProtocol` orchestrates a full run. Its `sample` method takes the `structure`, a `FlowModelWrapper`, a `TrajectorySampler`, a `StepScalerProtocol`, and a `reward`, then evolves one or more particles (optionally reweighting or resampling them along the trajectory using the `LossFunction`) and returns a `GuidanceOutput`. The final outputs of any run are generated from a `TrajectoryScalerProtocol`. `PureGuidance` is the base case: it applies the provided `StepScaler` guidance without resampling, generating an ensemble of structures. `FKSteering` adds Feynman-Kač resampling over a population of particles (where each particle is itself an ensemble) [7].

A `GuidanceOutput` standardizes the result of any run: the output `structure`, the `final_state` coordinates of shape `(*batch, atoms, 3)`, and optionally the full `trajectory`, the per-step `losses`, and arbitrary `metadata`.

4.4 Forward Models and LossFunctions

Forward models for experimental observables should take as input a set of arrays describing the coordinates, relevant structural model parameters (e.g. B-factors), and properties of the experimental data (e.g. resolution) and return the experimental observable. The calculations to obtain the experimental observable must be differentiable w.r.t. the inputs we want to apply guidance to, as we must calculate the gradient of the Loss function with respect to coordinates, and the Loss is a function of the experimental observable. The experimental observable should also be in a format that is easily writable to common data formats (e.g. CCP4 maps, MTZ files, MRC files) with existing libraries like `Gemmi`. If portions of the input are not specified (due to not being modeled in the initial structure, for example) we should utilize calculations like pseudo-B factor that estimate B-factor using confidence metrics from generative models. This B-factor (and parameters like occupancy) can then be optimized either during the guidance procedure or afterwards.

4.4.1 Loss Functions

Loss Functions in *sampleworks* should use a forward model to enable optimization of a target function. Loss Functions need to be ensemble-capable, in that they must be able to take a batch of structures as input.

In the current code state, we have implemented a `RealSpaceRewardFunction`, which enables minimization of the L1/L2 norm of the difference between a density map calculated from an input ensemble and a reference real-space electron-density map. You will notice that in this document we have referred to losses and rewards interchangeably, even though our implemented `RealSpaceRewardFunction` actually minimizes the output “reward”! We recognize

this is currently confusing, we will be standardizing on “loss” semantics as we move forward with updating the experimental loss function API. This portion of *sampleworks* is most subject to change as we explore additional types and sources of experimental data.

4.4.2 Composing multiple losses during guidance

Composing Loss functions should be easy and well defined for cases where multiple sources of experimental data are available for a given modeling task (e.g. we have a cryoEM map of a complex between two biomolecules and individual high-resolution datasets for the two components from crystallography), and the guidance should accommodate any Loss function with the protocol we define. At present the `sample()` interface accepts a single LossFunction, composition of multiple losses is not yet built in and is planned.

5 References

- [1] R. Wang and Y. Du, “Equilibrium Matching: Generative Modeling with Implicit Energy-Based Models,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2510.02300*, 2025, doi: [10.48550/arXiv.2510.02300](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2510.02300).
- [2] M. Balcerak and others, “Energy Matching: Unifying Flow Matching and Energy-Based Models,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2025. doi: [10.48550/arXiv.2504.10612](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2504.10612).
- [3] T. Karras, M. Aittala, T. Aila, and S. Laine, “Elucidating the Design Space of Diffusion-Based Generative Models,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2022. doi: [10.48550/arXiv.2206.00364](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2206.00364).
- [4] J. Abramson and others, “Accurate structure prediction of biomolecular interactions with AlphaFold 3,” *Nature*, vol. 630, pp. 493–500, 2024, doi: [10.1038/s41586-024-07487-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07487-w).
- [5] J. B. Ingraham and others, “Illuminating protein space with a programmable generative model,” *Nature*, vol. 623, pp. 1070–1078, 2023, doi: [10.1038/s41586-023-06728-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06728-8).
- [6] H. Chung, J. Kim, M. T. McCann, M. L. Klasky, and J. C. Ye, “Diffusion Posterior Sampling for General Noisy Inverse Problems,” in *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2023. doi: [10.48550/arXiv.2209.14687](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2209.14687).
- [7] R. Singhal and others, “A General Framework for Inference-time Scaling and Steering of Diffusion Models,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.06848*, 2025, doi: [10.48550/arXiv.2501.06848](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2501.06848).
- [8] M. Ren and others, “DriftLite: Lightweight Drift Control for Inference-Time Scaling of Diffusion Models,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2509.21655*, 2025, doi: [10.48550/arXiv.2509.21655](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2509.21655).
- [9] J. Wohlwend, G. Corso, and others, “Boltz-1: Democratizing Biomolecular Interaction Modeling,” *bioRxiv*, 2024, doi: [10.1101/2024.11.19.624167](https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.11.19.624167).
- [10] S. Passaro and others, “Boltz-2: Towards Accurate and Efficient Binding Affinity Prediction,” *bioRxiv*, 2025, doi: [10.1101/2025.06.14.659707](https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.06.14.659707).

APPENDIX A Example FlowModelWrapper for Boltz-2

Boltz2Wrapper implements the three `FlowModelWrapper` methods (`featurize`, `step`, and `initialize_from_prior`) for Boltz-2 [10]. We detail more about our implementation here to help developers incorporate new models into *sampleworks*.

A.1 featurize

`featurize` turns an Atomworks structure into everything the diffusion module needs downstream. Currently, it has a few side-effects. It writes a Boltz input YAML from the structure's `chain_info`, builds Boltz's inference data module, and runs a single Pairformer/trunk pass whose outputs are cached in a `BoltzConditioning` and reused unchanged across every denoising step:

```
1 def featurize(self, structure: dict) ->
  GenerativeModelInput[BoltzConditioning] python
```

The cached trunk outputs are exactly the conditioning the diffusion module consumes:

```
1 @dataclass(frozen=True, slots=True) python
2 class BoltzConditioning:
3     s: Tensor # single representation, [batch, tokens, dim]
4     z: Tensor # pair representation, [batch, tokens, tokens,
  dim]
5     s_inputs: Tensor # input embeddings
6     relative_position_encoding: Tensor
7     feats: dict[str, Any] # raw batch dict from the dataloader
8     diffusion_conditioning: dict[str, Tensor] | None = None # Boltz-2 only
```

The returned `GenerativeModelInput` pairs this conditioning with `x_init`. For Boltz-2, we use `x_init` to hold reference coordinates, so the wrapper sets `x_init` to the input structure coordinates from `featurize`.

A.2 step

`step` performs one denoising evaluation and returns the predicted clean sample \hat{x}_θ . Boltz operates on a padded atom layout, so the wrapper pads `x_t` up to the conditioning's `atom_pad_mask`, calls the diffusion module, and un pads the result back to the model's atom count:

```
1 def step( python
2     self,
3     x_t: Float[Tensor, "batch atoms 3"],
4     t: Float[Tensor, "*batch"],
5     *,
6     features: GenerativeModelInput[BoltzConditioning] | None = None,
7 ) -> Float[Tensor, "batch atoms 3"]
```

```
1 padded_x_t = pad_dim(x_t, dim=1, pad_len=pad_len) python
2 padded_atom_coords_denoised =
  self.model.structure_module.preconditioned_network_forward(
```

```

3     padded_x_t,
4     t_tensor,
5     network_condition_kwargs=dict(
6         multiplicity=padded_x_t.shape[0],
7         s_inputs=cond.s_inputs,
8         s_trunk=cond.s,
9         feats=feats,
10        diffusion_conditioning=cond.diffusion_conditioning,
11    ),
12 )
13 atom_coords_denoised =
    padded_atom_coords_denoised[atom_mask.bool(), :].reshape(x_t.shape[0], -1, 3)

```

`preconditioned_network_forward` applies the EDM input/output preconditioning [3] around the raw network, so its return value is already the \hat{x}_θ that the protocol requires.

A.3 initialize_from_prior

`initialize_from_prior` draws the starting noise. Boltz’s prior is an isotropic Gaussian, so the method simply samples `randn` shaped by the batch size and the atom count recovered from the cached `atom_pad_mask` (or an explicit shape):

```

1 def initialize_from_prior( python
2     self,
3     batch_size: int,
4     features: GenerativeModelInput[BoltzConditioning] | None = None,
5     *,
6     shape: tuple[int, ...] | None = None,
7 ) -> Float[Tensor, "batch atoms 3"]

```

Concerning alignment during sampling: experimental rewards are evaluated in the map’s reference frame, so the structure must be aligned to the density before the loss is computed. Boltz-2 currently relies on an initial structure to supply `x_init` as that alignment reference, but future work could instead align predictions using the density alone, removing the need for a starting model.